

Multimodal discontinuous reaction in Ni-Fe-Cr-Al alloy

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Abstract

Ni-Fe-Cr-Al alloy has been subjected to a short aging treatment, which increased the mechanical properties and resulted in discontinuous precipitation at the grain boundaries. In this study, analytical electron microscopy was applied to explore the relationship between the occurring grain boundary phenomena and mechanical behavior. Within the discontinuous precipitation zone, three different phases were recognized, namely γ solid solution with lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides and elongated γ' precipitates at the reaction front. Coherency of the discontinuous precipitates was identified as they have shown a cube-on-cube orientation relationship. Furthermore, the development of multiple discontinuous reactions was discussed.

Keywords

Nickel alloys; analytical electron microscopy; diffusion-induced grain boundary motion (DIGM); discontinuous precipitation

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An ongoing demand for more efficient power-related devices has been a driving force over the past few decades for the development of new high-temperature structural materials. It was stimulated by new production technologies, like additive manufacturing [1] and design strategies including high-entropy alloys [2] and Co-based superalloys [3]. However, the continuous chase for cost-optimal materials may result in more metastable microstructures, highly susceptible to undesired grain boundary reactions [4]. Among these reactions, discontinuous precipitation (DP) is a concept originating from cellular segregation proposed by Turnbull [5] and later described in detail by Cahn [6]. It results in the formation of a two-phase lamellar structure behind the migrating grain boundaries, determining the mechanical properties and high-temperature performance of materials. A formation of discontinuous precipitates has been reported in multiple binary and tertiary systems based on elements used in high-temperature materials, like Co, Fe and Ni [7], as well as in nickel-based superalloys [8–10].

Haynes[®] HR-224[®] (HR224) is a wrought Ni-Fe-Cr-Al alloy having a superior oxidation resistance when compared with similar heat-resistant alloys [11,12]. A potential application of this alloy includes heat recuperators, fuel cells and other severely oxidizing environments [13]. Although an outstanding environmental resistance of HR224 alloy was well established [11,14], there is a lack of information regarding the bulk material microstructure and heat treatment. In our study, we subjected HR224 alloy to a short aging treatment, which increased mechanical properties, but was charged with discontinuous precipitation at grain boundaries. Therefore, the present study is focused on the characterization of discontinuous precipitates formed in HR224 alloy and their strengthening potential.

A commercial wrought Haynes[®] HR-224[®] alloy was provided by Haynes International company in the form of 3.2 mm sheet in the solution treated condition. The nominal chemical composition of the investigated alloy was Ni-20Cr-27.5Fe-3.8Al-0.3Ti-0.3Si-0.05C (wt%). The as-received material was aged for 2 hours at temperatures between 600-900 °C followed by water quenching.

The mechanical response of HR224 alloy on the aging treatment was examined at room temperature static tensile tests. Non-standard, small bone-shaped specimens having a geometry as described in the previous study [15], were electrodischarge machined from aged sheets. The static tensile tests at a constant strain rate of $6.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ were performed using Zwick Roell AllroundLine Z10 machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell and a dedicated specimen grips. The laserXtens HP1-15 speckle-type laser extensometer combined with optical cameras was applied for non-contact strain measurements.

The influence of aging on the microstructural evolution was characterized by various electron microscopy and spectroscopy techniques. Samples for scanning electron microscope (SEM) investigation were mechanically ground and polished with a colloidal silica suspension. For electrochemical etching, a 10% mixture of oxalic acid in distilled water was used. The SEM images were acquired using a high-resolution SEM Merlin Gemini II (ZEISS) equipped with a Schottky field-emission gun.

Thin foils for the transmission- and scanning transmission electron microscopy (TEM/STEM) analyses were prepared using a conventional twin-jet electropolishing utilizing a Tenupol 5 (Struers) apparatus. For electropolishing, a mixture of perchloric acid and glacial acetic acid (1:10 ratio) was used at 10 °C temperature and polarization of 50 V. The TEM/STEM investigation was performed using a Tecnai G2 20 TWIN and a probe Cs-corrected Titan³ G2 60-300 with ChemiSTEM system (both FEI microscopes). The STEM images were acquired using a high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector. The phase identification was done using selected area electron diffraction (SAED) combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) and calculation using JEMS software. The EDXS data were acquired at 200 kV, then analyzed utilizing Esprit 1.9 software (Bruker), where a standardless Cliff-Lorimer quantification method was used.

The microstructure of the as-received HR224 alloy was characterized by a ~20 μm equiaxed grains (Fig. 1a) of Ni-based γ solid solution. Additionally, a small amount of randomly distributed primary MC carbides was observed along with fine, blocky M₂₃C₆ carbides present mainly at grain boundaries (Fig. 1b). Moreover, some serrated grain boundaries were recognized, indicating the presence of some undissolved particles after annealing.

Figures 1c-f show the evolution of grain boundary precipitates with the aging temperature. Similar morphology of grain boundary precipitates was observed between 600 and 800 °C, where duplex, discontinuous precipitates were recognized. At the lowest aging temperature of 600 °C, grain boundary precipitates reached a length of about 1 μm behind the moving grain boundaries (Fig. 1c), while at higher temperatures it was up to 5 μm (Fig. 1d,e). At the highest aging temperature, only regular M₂₃C₆ carbides were observed at the grain boundaries (Fig. 1f).

Figure 1. SEM secondary electron image of the HR224 alloy microstructure in the as-received condition (a, b) and after aging for 2 hrs at 600 °C (c), 700 °C (d), 800 °C (e), 900 °C (f). The results of the room temperature tensile test of HR224 alloy in the function of aging temperature; AR corresponds to as-received condition (g).

Change of ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the total elongation upon applied 2 hrs aging procedure were compared with that of the as-received material and plotted in Fig. 1g. The HR224 alloy in the as-received condition was characterized by UTS on the level of 736 MPa and total elongation of 49%. Although, the tensile tests were performed using non-standard specimens, the obtained results were in remarkable agreement with producer's reference values of solid solution annealed material (UTS = 732 MPa; elongation of 47%, respectively [13]). The 2-hour aging treatment increased UTS up to 922 MPa at 800 °C and simultaneously decreased the elongation down to 33%. The highest aging temperature of 900 °C resulted in a decrease of both UTS and the total elongation decreased to 700 MPa and 47%, respectively, as compared to the solid-solution annealed condition. Notably, a similar value of elongation was recorded for specimen aged at 600 °C (46%), however UTS in this sample increased up to 830 MPa.

By taking into account, that samples aged between 600 and 800 °C showed an increase of mechanical strength it was concluded that this change was, to some extent, induced by the presence of discontinuous precipitates at the grain boundaries and growth of these precipitates. It should be also affected by precipitation of the γ' phase, however, an increase of UTS was also observed in the sample aged at 600 °C, i.e. where γ' phase within grains volumes was absent. Therefore, further considerations will be focused on the grain boundary precipitation phenomena.

Firstly, a matter of fine precipitates at the grain boundary was evaluated in HR224 alloys aged for 2 hrs at 700 °C (Fig 2). Corresponding SAED patterns were taken from areas marked as 1 and 2 in the TEM bright-field (TEM-BF) image, while the highlighted solution for both patterns is shown on the right. The first SEAD pattern, taken from the grain on the right in the TEM-BF image clearly showed a solution for $\gamma+\gamma'$ phases in $[0\ 0\ 1]$ zone axis. The second SAED pattern, taken from the area of grain boundary precipitate combined with the grain on the right. Additional spots, when compared to the first SAED pattern, were solved as fcc Cr_{23}C_6 carbide (ISCD-2837) in $[0\ 0\ 1]$ zone axis. The lattice parameter of Cr_{23}C_6 carbide (10.65 Å) is almost exactly thrice greater than the lattice parameter of the γ phase (3.57 Å, JEMS data), which explains the $(0\ 2\ 0)_{\gamma}$ and $(0\ 6\ 0)_{\text{Cr}_{23}\text{C}_6}$ spots overlap and is attributed as a cube-on-cube orientation relationship: $(0\ 0\ 1)_{\text{Cr}_{23}\text{C}_6} \parallel (0\ 0\ 1)_{\gamma}$ and $[0\ 0\ 1]_{\text{Cr}_{23}\text{C}_6} \parallel [0\ 0\ 1]_{\gamma}$. Notably, there was no orientation relationship between the grain on the left side of the TEM-BF image and the previously discussed microstructural elements.

Figure 2. TEM-BF image of HR224 alloy aged for 2 hrs at 700 °C with fine Cr_{23}C_6 carbides at the grain boundary. Selected area electron diffraction patterns were taken from areas marked as 1 and 2 in the TEM-BF image. The solution for both diffraction patterns is shown on the right, where the black dot in the middle corresponds to the central spot, red circles to the γ phase, while orange and blue dots to γ' phase and Cr_{23}C_6 carbides, respectively.

Secondly, a case of discontinuous precipitation was analyzed (Fig. 3). Figure 3a shows the TEM-BF image of HR224 alloy aged for 2 hrs at 700 °C, where DP at the grain boundary was about 2-3 μm long. Initially, the dual-phase nature of the DP was recognized, where parallel needles of Cr_{23}C_6 carbides were present in the γ matrix. Subsequently, fine, Cr_{23}C_6 carbides were observed at the dislocation boundary formed between the DP zone and original grain, as indicated by yellow dashed lines. The misorientation angle between the dislocation boundary and the boundary suspending the growth of DP front (Fig. 3a) was slightly less than 15 degrees. Moreover, dislocation movement along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction was only partially blocked by fine carbides, leading to the formation of dislocation pile-ups and a continuation of dislocation glide in the adjacent area. Notably, the dislocation pile-ups were parallel to the lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides present within the DP zone. The SAED pattern was solved for γ , γ' and Cr_{23}C_6 phases in a $[1\ 1\ 2]$ zone axis, as shown in Fig. 3d. The red circle in the SAED pattern shows the spots used to obtain the TEM dark field (TEM-DF) image (Fig. 3e). All four spots within the circle correspond to Cr_{23}C_6 carbides, demonstrated as bright precipitates at the dislocation boundary and as lamellar precipitates within the DP.

Figure 3. (a) Discontinuous precipitation at the grain boundary in HR224 alloy aged for 2 hrs at 700 °C (TEM-BF); (b) Highlighted area at the dislocation boundary indicated by the dashed box in Fig. 3a (TEM-BF); (c) Selected area electron diffraction pattern taken from the area marked with a blue circle in Fig. 3b; (d) Solution for diffraction pattern present in Fig. 3c; (e) TEM-DF image of Cr_{23}C_6 carbides in discontinuous precipitation, aperture position for DF imaging was indicated by the red circle in Fig. 3c.

Lastly, Figure 4 shows a STEM-HAADF image of DP along with STEM-EDXS elemental maps of Ni, Cr, Fe and Al. The STEM-EDXS results show a clear separation between three phases, where preferential partitioning of Ni, Cr and Fe was observed. The Cr-rich regions

correspond to the precipitation of lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides, which were present across the DP zone. Furthermore, lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides were surrounded by either Ni- and Al-rich zones or Fe-rich zones at the reaction front, indicating the presence of elongated γ' precipitates alternated by precipitation free zones. The intensity of STEM-EDXS elemental maps suggests a low solubility of both Ni and Fe in Cr_{23}C_6 carbides and moderate presence of Ni in γ solid solution and Fe in γ' phase. Complementing, Cr presented low solubility in the γ' phase and moderate in the γ phase.

Figure 4. STEM-HAADF image of discontinuous precipitation at the grain boundary in HR224 alloys aged for 2 hrs at 700 °C with corresponding STEM-EDXS distribution maps of selected elements.

In general, the discontinuous reaction (DR) process has been defined by Williams and Butler [16] as the formation of a solute-depleted phase and a precipitate phase as a duplex, usually lamellar, transformation product behind a grain boundary advancing into the supersaturated matrix. Authors distinguished three main solid-state DRs, later classified by Zięba and Gust [17] as discontinuous precipitation, coarsening, dissolution and complemented by diffusion-induced grain boundary migration (DIGM). Furthermore, all the above-mentioned reactions result in the formation of up to two-phase DR product, while we found that in the investigated Ni-Fe-Cr-Al system DP resulted in the formation of a three-phase DR product. Consequently, lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides were present within the γ matrix of the DP zone, along with γ' precipitates located mainly at the reaction front (Figs 3, 4). These findings are comparable to those of Heckl et al. [10,18] and Nystrom et al. [9] who reported a three-phase DP in high-refractory nickel-based superalloys. In both studies, the γ and γ' phases were present within the DP zone, but as the third phase, they reported topologically close-packed (TCP) phases. Moreover, they found γ' phase in the whole volume of the DP, while in our study

presence of the γ' phase should be associated rather with the reaction front, than the volume of the DP. This may be explained by a different initial microstructure, where a high volume of the γ' phase was already present, while in the present study the as-received material was solution treated and contained only γ phase and carbides. Furthermore, in our as-received material serrated grain boundaries were observed (Fig. 1b) indicating a source of the solute atoms to initiate the DIGM [17]. It is reasonable to assume, that the DIGM was the main trigger of the DP process and was followed by the precipitation of lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides and later γ' precipitates. To some extent, one may classify previously mentioned studies [9,10,18] as a discontinuous coarsening of γ and γ' phases combined with the precipitation of TCP phases, while in the present study double DP process occurred. A higher concentration of TCP phases may decrease the mechanical properties of alloys [19], while in the investigated Ni-Fe-Cr-Al alloy, samples aged at 600-800 °C, i.e. developing DP at the grain boundaries (Fig.1) demonstrated an increase of UTS in comparison to the as-received material. Partially this was associated with precipitation of the γ' phase within the γ grains at 700 and 800 °C, however, the increase of UTS was also observed for sample aged at 600 °C (Fig. 1g).

The SAED analysis revealed that the small Cr_{23}C_6 carbides (Fig. 2), as well as the lamellar ones in the DP zone and those located at the original dislocation boundary (Fig. 3), showed well known [20,21] cube-on-cube orientation relationship with the γ matrix. Furthermore, slip bands along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction (Fig. 3a) were parallel to lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides indicating the growth of these precipitates along this direction. Li et al. [20,22] reported a similar orientation relationship between the DP and the γ/γ' grain behind the migrating boundary in nickel-based superalloy, which resulted in the coarsening of γ' phase along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction. Growth of the DP along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction in the nickel-based alloy was also reported by Spadotto et al. [8,23], who investigated Ni-Fe-Cr-N alloy (Nicrofer 3033 or Alloy 33) aged between 700 - 900 °C. Authors showed that in the initial stage growth of the Cr-rich M_{23}C_6 carbides was perpendicular to the migrating grain boundary, however, later it was suppressed by the growth of lamellar, bcc α -Cr. Nevertheless, some coherency was still preserved, as they have reported the Kurdjumov-Sachs orientation relationship, where $(\bar{1} 1 0)_{\alpha\text{-Cr}} \parallel (\bar{1} 1 1)_{\gamma}$ and $[1 1 1]_{\alpha\text{-Cr}} \parallel [1 0 1]_{\gamma}$. In our study, full coherency maintained between the Cr_{23}C_6 carbides and γ matrix, which offers an understanding of enhanced mechanical properties resulting from the DP process.

Recently, Atrazhev et al. [24] proposed a model based on the classical concept of grain boundary DP [6] to describe the formation of fan-type structure in nickel-based superalloys, which involves an alternate growth of elongated “fans” of γ and γ' phases. Although in our

study the DP mode was different, a comparable fan-type structure of γ/γ' phases was observed at the reaction front (Fig. 4). Authors pointed out that the formation of such structure requires a relatively slow cooling rate and high grain boundary mobility, therefore reaction front at low-angle grain boundary would meet those conditions.

In summary, our findings provide new insight into discontinuous reactions at the grain boundaries in the Ni-Fe-Cr-Al system. The titular “multimodal discontinuous precipitation” can be understood in two ways. On one hand, we observed the formation of three phases in the DP, which is a deviation from the classical two-phase reaction product. On the other hand, various discontinuous reaction modes were recognized. In the DP, the γ matrix contained lamellar precipitates of Cr_{23}C_6 carbides and elongated γ' precipitates alternated by precipitation free zones at the reaction front. Additionally, lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides, as well as those located at the original dislocation boundary exhibit a cube-on-cube orientation relationship with the γ grain, where $(0\ 0\ 1)_{\text{Cr}_{23}\text{C}_6} \parallel (0\ 0\ 1)_{\gamma}$ and $[0\ 0\ 1]_{\text{Cr}_{23}\text{C}_6} \parallel [0\ 0\ 1]_{\gamma}$. The discontinuous reaction should originate from the grain boundary serrations present after the solution treatment, which resulted in diffusion induced grain boundary migration. Later this reaction was followed by precipitation of lamellar Cr_{23}C_6 carbides along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction and γ' precipitates at the reaction front. The presence of coherent precipitates at the grain boundary resulted in an increase of mechanical strength after aging at temperatures between 600-800 °C.

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Figure 1. SEM secondary electron image of the HR224 alloy microstructure in the as-received condition (a, b) and after aging for 2 hrs at 600 °C (c), 700 °C (d), 800 °C (e), 900 °C (f). The results of the room temperature tensile test of HR224 alloy in the function of aging temperature; AR corresponds to as-received condition (g).

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